

THE EFFECT OF GLOBAL CHALLENGE, MANAGERIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGE TO INCREASE COMPETITIVENESS AND HUMAN RESOURCE PERFORMANCE IN THE COVID-19 ERA

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Abstract

The Covid-19 pandemic has compelled quarantine orders to be implemented globally. Currently, the pandemic will shifting to be endemic that affect many sector of policies, innovations, adaptations, and procedures in economic sector. Especially in human resources field create an innovation to answer the global challenge. This study emphasis on identifying and overcoming the effect of global challenge on increasing the competitiveness and human resources performance due to COVID-19. The population in this study are millennials generation employees in South Sulawesi, Indonesia. The sampling technique utilized is proportional random sampling and analyzing with an associative quantitative descriptive. Data collected through questionnaires distributed to millennial generation employees. The result of this study show the competitiveness and Human resource performance can be improved by giving first, e-training, e-leadership, and work-life balance. Second, e-training, e-leadership, work-life balance, and work motivation have positive effect on managerial and environmental challenge. The findings indicate that companies must pay attention to the kind of e-training, e-leadership, and work-life balance to keep employees motivated and to maintain optimal employee performance, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic through working online.

Keywords: Competitiveness and Performance, Human Resources, Covid-19

Classification codes: M10

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 epidemic has had a significant effect on every area of the global economy. It has had severe implication for business sector especially in human resources performance. The emerge of COVID-19 has disrupted many activities and requires intense and prompt attention from economic sector. Currently, human resource leaders face the difficult task of managing the interest of workers and their corporations. The breakout of COVID-19 has demonstrated that this is not just a challenging period but rather a testing time for organizations across the globe to verify and assure how rapidly they adjust themselves by thinking and preparing differently. An enterprise evolves with nature, and change is necessary if performance, competitiveness, and productivity are to improve. Changes in structure, technology and priorities are overgrowing, providing enormous hurdles to leaders. Corporations worldwide have looked to technology to find imaginative solutions to some of the world's most serious problems.

In the era of the global economy, the intense competition between businesses heightens the difficulty of being at the forefront of the industry and offering superior customer service. Employees are urged to perform effectively and contribute to the company's growth. In light of current trends, organizations are hiring members of the millennial generation, who were born between 1980 and 2000. Millennials are portrayed as technology-savvy, eager to succeed rapidly, prone to give up, and seeking instant pleasure. This is undoubtedly distinct from prior generations and is one of the new difficulties facing the global workforce (Pyoria, Ojala, Saari, and Jarvinen, 2017).

Millennials were born between 1980 and 2000 (Murphy, Gibson, & Greenwood, 2010; Schultz, Schwepker, & Good, 2012). Millennium is a generation of young people characterized by the usage and application of technology in their daily lives, as well as values, life experiences, motivation, and general buying behavior (Smith & Nichols, 2015; Yigit & Aksay, 2015). This generation is a group of customers and residents of the world who have been dubbed as Generation Y, Millennial, and Echo Boom (Moreno, Lafuente, Carreón, & Moreno, 2017).

The COVID-19 pandemic increasingly triggers an intense competitiveness among companies challenged to achieve optimal performance for millennial generation. Moreover, the competitiveness and unpredictable situation requires new human resources practices to deal with the problems in the organizations to enhance their climate, contribute, and innovation performance. Researcher declared that the managerial and environmental economic theory is widely implemented in competitiveness and human resource performance to support organization's practice, proficiency, and competencies. Due to the pandemic COVID-19 the government implementing lockdown and all economic sector are shifting into either electronic or digital device. Many employee work from home as the alternative solution to prevent the spreading of the virus. Even though the pandemic has been attacked around the world, but the economic organization should act effectively and efficiently using relevant knowledge and innovation by utilizing information technology to manage the human resources to remain sustainable (Christa & Kristinae, 2021).

Globally, the crisis necessitated that employees possess the technological abilities necessary to execute their duties remotely. In addition, managers were required to acquire the skills necessary to motivate and direct their employees in this new environment (Nesterova, 2021). While discussing NHRM practices and innovation performance, Laursen and Foss (Laursen & Foss, 2003) have mentioned the complementarities between several technologies and learning. In light of the fact that crises are opportunities, decision-makers must act swiftly (Guderian, Bican & Riar, 2021). Furthermore, to expand the process of competitiveness, innovation, and human resource performance the organization should share novel training in managing the knowledge and skill sources such as providing exceptional training and attending workshop to attain organizational performance and full of spark innovation. There are several aspect to this study related to the improvement of millennials employee generation during the pandemic period.

The first aspect is e-training where the latest years the use of internet and computer has greatly affect the employee. Not only for working, in the educational sector introduced e-learning as a

teaching method and has a significant impact on attract quality human capital and achieve a competitive advantage (Menon, 2015). However, the e-training should be continuously supported by practicing and gaining technological skills for all staff and employee. Grencikova et al. (2020) mentioned the biggest challenge that faced human resource management practices was addressing the shortage of qualified, skilled, and motivated individuals in the global labor market. e-training mimics e-learning in many aspects, particularly in terms of the delivery method and technology employed, except that it typically refers to a much shorter learning duration meant to attain a certain learning objective or skill (Ramayah, Ahmad, & Hong, 2012). E-training is defined as a process of distance training through the use of the Internet or Intranet that equips individuals with the necessary knowledge regarding their chosen disciplines (Amara & Atia, 2016).

The second aspect in managerial and environmental challenge is e-leadership. Young employee that categorized as millennials have arduous to be loyal and committed to the industry because its defining characteristics include liberty, adaptability, discussion, open communication with superiors and coworkers, and the application of technology. Companies must now consider the significance of adjusting and adapting the manager's leadership strategy toward its team, which is comprised of millennials on average (Mansor, Mun, Farhana, and Tarmiz, 2017; Putriastuti and Stasi, 2019; Valenti, 2019).

Third is improve work motivation, There is a close connection between motivation, action or behavior needs, goals, as well as satisfaction and performance. Previous research has demonstrated that work motivation has a major impact on performance (Nguyen et al., 2020). The purpose of this study is to assess the effectiveness of e-training, e-leadership, work-life balance, and work motivation on the performance of millennial generation employees in today's work-life, in light of the COVID-19 outbreak, which necessitates more online work, utilizing quantitative methodology to support this research. Then, we present and discuss the implications of our empirical analysis.

Competitiveness and human resource performance practice have flexibility and inventiveness to deal with managerial and environmental challenge. The research have revealed a significant positive relationship linking human resource performance, competitiveness, e-training, and leadership practices and innovation performance in organizations based on IT- techniques ((Waheed, A.; Miao, X.; Waheed, S.; Ahmad, N.; Majeed, 2019; Waheed, A.; Xiaoming, M.; Ahmad, N.; Waheed, S., 2020); further, organizational sustainability depends on constant innovation. Innovation appears as is a significant technological tool that can upgrade in a new context over time (Waheed, A.; Miao, X.; Waheed, S.; Ahmad, N.; Majeed, 2019), During the COVID-19 period in the economic sector (Ebersbeger & Kuckertz, 2021). By following this idea, plus the light of former literature, our current study proposes the managerial and environmental challenge in increasing competitiveness and human resource performance in the economic sector during the COVID-19 pandemic.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The current research adopted quantitative descriptive method, followed by literature review approach. The population in this study is millennials employee at South Sulawesi, Indonesia. The sample was chosen by proportional random sampling technique methods. According to the Sugiyono, (2017) proportional random sampling is a technique of taking sample from a population members using a random method without regard to the strata in the population. The method taken by drawing the research sample.

In this study data collected through observations and online questionnaires distributed to the participants. A google form questionnaire was sent to employee via emails and social media channel such as WhatsApp employee group. Due to the COVID pandemic, rapid data acquisition is a need (Alsoud & Harasis, 2021). Online surveys are becoming a popular, accessible, and speedy method for collecting data and analyzing results at a cheaper cost and with fewer errors than manual instruments. Also, mobile surveys on smartphones are frequently more convenient for respondents (Maymore et al, 2012).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In times of trouble, a skilled employee is needed to give the great performance of organization. The acts of HR pioneers during the COVID-19 epidemic will have a big impact on their respective firms. When COVID-19 spread over the world, HR departments made the health and safety of their employees a key priority. The long-term viability of HRM can be determined by how they respond to the current crisis. Cloud computing and other web-based solutions will also address a critical resource allocation gap. It demonstrates the potential efficacy of patient-focused, web-based applications based on result-driven design, which requires further testing and validation.

Based on the result, the effect of e-training on employee is positive which has mean 0.7 gained from 120 respondents. They said that during the pandemic one must remain productive and continue to work as intended even though it is done from inside the house. The millennial generation finds it easy to do work from home by utilizing existing technology. They even feel happy when they get additional training related to the use of the latest technology to support their work activities. A total of 89 participants said they agreed about the use of e-training that was applied during the pandemic. The existence of e-training helps their work to be more effective. So it can be said that there is sufficient evidence that e-training has a positive effect on employee performance.

The findings of this investigation support previous research the results of this study support Kamal's findings that the primary goal of e-training is to improve employee performance and employee happiness in order to develop a productive workforce (Kamal, Aghbari, & Atteia, 2016). E-training is a human resource management strategy for enhancing employee performance (Hila et al., 2017). E-training can be useful for enhancing employee performance because employees can access training resources from anywhere in the globe via the Internet (Christian, Krieger, Holzinger, & Behringer, 2007). In addition, this study confirms what Hila

et al. (2017) stated, that e-training can enhance employee job enthusiasm and stimulate engagement in corporate activities (Razak, Yusop, Perumal, & Chukumaran, 2015). According to Kabbasi's research, e-training can increase employee engagement and performance. She said that digital literacy and media savvy are required for success in all part of life, including the workplace (Kabassi & Virvou, 2004).

The next indicator in the survey is e-leadership training to add insight and remind workers' skills. Millennials are at an age that is easy to adapt and absorb new knowledge or knowledge. So that when given training in the form of e-leadership, they will train their leadership spirit at work. Based on the survey results, 79 respondents agreed that the implementation of e-leadership increases employee confidence. A good sense of self-confidence combined with the ability to operate technology will be able to produce good performance. According to Avolio's (Avolio, Kahai, & Dodge, 2001) research, e-leadership is a combination of leadership context and technology that contributes to and optimizes employee performance. The findings of this study support this definition. Hema and Gupta added that e-leadership is a new paradigm that offers numerous new opportunities, such as the ability to communicate directly with employees, customers, and suppliers using technology to enhance performance (Hema & Gupta, 2015). E-leadership adapts and integrates virtuality in order to guarantee the success and performance of its employees (Darics, 2020; Fernández & Jawadi, 2015).

The influence of work motivation is positive and significant with 87 out of 120 participants say agree. Thus, it can be said that e-leadership has a positive effect on work motivation to increase the competitiveness. The participants said that they feel comfortable to do work where the place they are working is giving the motivation. If the motivation increase the creativity will come along. This matter supported young employee to have the strong competitiveness. According to the Gupta and Hema (2015), work motivation can increase the faithfulness of employee. Hence, the millennials employee are categorized as modern generation who love using technology in their daily life. The collaboration of creativity and technology will produced the good performance. However, the effect of work motivation on employee performance is positive and significant to increase the human resource performance. The findings of this study support the hypothesis that the proper motivation for employees will affect their performance (Oren et al., 2013). This study's findings are also compatible with research conducted by Pancasila, who concluded that motivation is directly tied to the creation of a propensity to work hard and perform well in order to accomplish goals (Pancasila et al., 2020). John's research also demonstrates that employee performance is affected by work motivation (John et al., 2012).

The next survey question is about the effect of the level stress on employee will reduce if organization giving attention to their employee. It could cause the work-life balance among the millennial employee influence the welfare. So that, they could work without any burden to them and their relatives. This study supported by Aryes's research which control over work and family role roles could improve human resource performance that leads to job satisfaction (Arye, Tan, & Srinivas, 2005). Dash said the negative effects when employees work excessively, namely, high absenteeism, decreased productivity, and decreased performance

(Darko-Asumadu, Sika-Bright, & Osei-Tutu, 2018; Dhas, 2015). Employee work-life balance helps in reducing stress levels at work and increasing employee performance (R et al., 2015). Darcy's research states that work and life balance can affect the level of employee performance in the organization (Darcy, Mccarthy, Hill, & Grady, 2012).

CONCLUSIONS

Pandemic Covid-19 has created a fear of the unknown in all individuals. All businesses around the globe including human resource performances sector are adversely affected because of lockdown and quarantine orders. The current study concludes that new human resource management practices are an essential tool in the economic sector to fulfill the economic and environmental challenge during the pandemic. The result of this study show the competitiveness and Human resource performance can be improved by giving first, e-training, e-leadership, and work-life balance. Second, e-training, e-leadership, work-life balance, and work motivation have positive effect on managerial and environmental challenge. The findings indicate that companies must pay attention to the kind of e-training, e-leadership, and work-life balance to keep employees motivated and to maintain optimal employee performance, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic through working online.

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